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Empirical Evidence of the Effects of Climate Change on NCDs: A Literature Review

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Abstract: Recent years have seen a surge in research on climate change and its health impacts, highlighting the growing urgency of this issue. As climate change intensifies extreme weather events (EWEs), non-communicable diseases (NCDs) may also be exacerbated. This systematic review of 152 papers examines the effects of EWEs on NCDs. Heatwaves are associated with increased mortality from stroke, ischaemic heart disease, and respiratory conditions, though findings on morbidity are mixed. Wildfires could worsen respiratory diseases through air pollution and contribute to mental health issues, including anxiety and depression. Recurrent floods indicate long-term psychological impacts. Droughts, while harder to quantify, could lead to heat-related illnesses and mental stress due to economic hardship. Also, studies suggest that storms increase cardiovascular and respiratory risks, while also contributing to mental health problems. Vulnerable groups, particularly older adults and socioeconomically disadvantaged populations are disproportionately affected due to pre-existing conditions and limited healthcare access. Future research should focus on refining research designs and methodologies to better capture the impacts of specific EWEs on NCDs. Improved measurement and the use of direct climate change indicators, rather than proxies, could also enhance the precision of findings.

Keywords: climate change; extreme weather event; natural disaster; non-communicable disease; health

JEL Classification: I15; Q54; Q56; I18

1 Introduction

Earth's climate has been gradually yet persistently changing due to various geological and atmospheric processes. Over the past 65 million years, alternating warm and

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cool periods, along with occasional abrupt shifts, have been identified through deep-sea sediment analysis (Zachos et al. 2001). However, since the 20th century, these natural changes have accelerated. Global warming, characterized by the gradual rise in Earth's surface temperature, is considered the primary driver of contemporary climate change (Hansen et al. 2010). This warming trend is evident from indicators such as rising sea levels and increasing global land, air, and sea temperatures (NASA 2024). The resulting temperature increase has contributed to more frequent extreme weather events (EWEs), such as heatwaves, wildfires, air pollution, floods, droughts, and storms (Berlemann and Steinhardt 2017). For instance, a recent study reports that the frequency of extreme wildfires has more than doubled from 2003 to 2023, with six of the most intense events occurring in the past 7 years (Cunningham, Williamson, and Bowman 2024).

These EWEs impact human health in both direct and indirect ways (Berlemann and Eurich 2022). Indirect effects lead to changes in socio-economic characteristics of the population like education or employment. Direct effects are due to actual exposure of the population by virtue of spatial proximity to the EWEs resulting in natural disasters. These direct effects are identified through devastation of human habitation and infrastructure, along with morbidity (aggravation of existing diseases) and mortality (death). Moreover, these disasters create environmental conditions that can affect even healthy populations, exposing them to unfamiliar diseases and exacerbating pre-existing health issues.

These diseases are commonly known as non-communicable diseases (NCD) such as cardiovascular diseases, respiratory disorders, diabetes, and mental health issues (World Health Organization 2023). Unlike communicable diseases such as AIDS, malaria, and COVID-19, NCDs are chronic and non-infectious. Their development is often linked to a combination of physiological, behavioural, genetic, and environmental factors, the latter being the focus of this paper. Cardiovascular diseases include coronary artery disease, hypertension, heart failure, and stroke, while common respiratory conditions are chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma. Mental health disorders range from depression and anxiety to bipolar disorder and schizophrenia. NCDs are highly relevant to this study, as the increasing frequency and intensity of EWEs driven by climate change seems to significantly impact their prevalence and severity (Liu et al. 2010; Peduzzi et al. 2012; Perkins-Kirkpatrick and Lewis 2020; Tellman et al. 2021; Trenberth et al. 2014; Weilhhammer et al. 2021).

The potential impact of EWEs on the prevalence and severity of NCDs may be particularly relevant in the case of heatwaves. As one of the more direct manifestations of climate change, heatwaves are thought to contribute to an increased risk of cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. Understanding how heatwaves are defined and measured is crucial to assessing their health impacts. Heatwaves are identified using various metrics depending on the research question. One common approach is

percentile-based definitions, which set thresholds relative to historical temperature distributions, taking local climate variations into account. Another method involves absolute temperature thresholds, which use fixed temperature limits that allow for consistent criteria across different regions. Some studies define heatwaves using a heat index and apparent temperature, which account for perceived temperatures, including both heat and humidity, providing a more accurate representation of human exposure. Additionally, some approaches use climatological periods and variability, identifying specific periods based on climatological analysis or considering temperature variability to account for prolonged heat exposure (for more details, see Section 4.1). These indicators have been linked to higher mortality rates and increased hospital admissions for cardiovascular and respiratory conditions (Barnett et al. 2012; Chen et al. 2015; Sheridan and Lin 2014; Turner, Connell, and Tong 2013; Zeng et al. 2014).

Wildfires release air pollutants, including particulate matter and other toxic gases, which could aggravate respiratory issues and potentially trigger cardiovascular events (Caamano-Isorna et al. 2011). Socioeconomically disadvantaged populations are more vulnerable to these effects than other segments of the population. Air pollution from wildfires exacerbates existing illnesses and the impact varies depending on the topography and inhabitation. Additionally, anthropogenic intervention such as deforestation aggravates the severity of wildfires.

Floods could disrupt healthcare access and food security, leading to worsened chronic health conditions and mental health issues (Agache et al. 2022). These events may contribute to increased rates of common mental disorders, such as anxiety and depression (Graham et al. 2019). The stress associated with floods may stem from property damage, displacement, and the subsequent recovery process that in turn aggravate existing health conditions and hinders effective management of NCDs (Lamond, Joseph, and Proverbs 2015).

Similarly, storms and droughts could pose significant health risks by exacerbating existing health problems. Storms may limit access to essential healthcare services during peak treatment periods, especially due to inadequate treatment capacity or damaged healthcare infrastructure and transportation issues in affected areas. Droughts may lead to a gradual degradation of socioeconomic status, largely due to income loss, which could contribute to mental health problems, especially in rural regions and among those directly or indirectly dependent on agricultural production for their livelihood (Moyo et al. 2023). In turn, such EWEs limit access to healthcare systems for the financially deprived populations, making them more vulnerable to such health risks. For detailed discussion, see Section 4.4 for droughts and Section 4.5 for storms.

This paper aims to systematically review and analyse the empirical evidence regarding the effects of climate change on NCDs. By examining studies from various geographical regions and climate contexts, it seeks to provide a comprehensive

understanding of how climate change leads to EWEs which in turn influence NCDs to offer insights that can inform effective public health strategies and interventions. We find that the impact of climate-related disasters on NCDs is increasingly discussed in the scientific literature. The growing body of research on this topic highlights the need to explore its heterogeneity across different EWEs, NCDs, and affected populations.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 discusses the method used for gathering literature from various online sources and explains how the most relevant literature is selected for further analysis. Various aspects of this retained literature are discussed in Section 3. Section 4 performs a systematic review of this retained literature to understand how climate change leads to EWEs which in turn influence NCDs. Section 5 provides a conclusion.

2 Methods

We conduct a systematic review synthesizing scientific and empirical evidence regarding the effects of climate change on NCDs. Our methodology follows the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 framework, which provides a structured approach to identifying, screening, and including relevant studies (Page et al. 2021). This method ensures transparency and reproducibility in our review process. It involves the identification of relevant studies via databases, registers, and sources, the screening of the collected studies, and the assessment of their eligibility. In the following chapter, we describe the application of the PRISMA method in more detail.

2.1 Search Strategy

To gather relevant studies, we systematically search three databases: Web of Science, PubMed, and Scopus. We chose these three databases for our literature review as these collectively provide extensive coverage of scholarly literature in the field, including peer-reviewed articles, conference proceedings, and other academic publications.

The search terms used encompass a broad range of climate phenomena and terms implicating potential impacts on various NCDs, including mental health issues, cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, and other non-communicable diseases.

The search string used is:

("climate change" OR "global warming" OR "pollution") AND ("human" OR "anthropogenic") AND ("disaster" OR "heat wave" OR "heatwave" OR "hurricane" OR "wildfire" OR "flood" OR "drought" OR "storm" OR "heavy rain" OR "catastrophe" OR "cyclone") AND ("dissatisfaction" OR "hospitalization" OR "cardiovascular" OR "respiratory" OR "mental health" OR "ncd" OR "non-communicable" OR "psychological" OR "depression" OR "stress" OR "anxiety").

We included the terms "human" and "anthropogenic" to focus specifically on human health outcomes and exclude results primarily related to agricultural or livestock studies. To encompass the mental health aspect of NCDs, we incorporated terms such as "psychological", "depression", "stress", "anxiety", "dissatisfaction", and the bigram "mental health". For climate change indicators, we employed a range of terms including "climate change", "global warming", and "pollution", as well as specific extreme weather events often associated with climate change: "disaster", "heat wave", "heatwave", "hurricane", "wildfire", "flood", "drought", "storm", "heavy rain", "catastrophe", and "cyclone".

2.2 Data Extraction and Synthesis

Based on the search results from all three databases, we initially retrieved 2,944 studies. We developed a custom script using the software tool R to consolidate the results into a structured, merged database, extract relevant details, and systematically screen for duplicates. After this process, we identified 1,906 unique studies. For each entry, we extracted key information such as bibliographic details (title, authors, year, source, volume, issue), abstract, identifiers (DOI, PubMed ID), and metadata (affiliations, keywords, document type, open access status). Additionally, we included 46 more references identified through citations in other papers.

Three researchers independently reviewed and analysed the collected studies, screening them for relevance and excluding those that did not meet the following criteria:

Reason 1: The article is not directly related to the topic.

Reason 2: The article is not in English.

In case where reports were not retrievable due to reasons such as broken links, retraction, or incorrect citations, or were not eligible according to our criteria, we removed them from our sample.

Finally, we include 151 articles in our review. The detailed steps of our literature search and screening process are illustrated in the PRISMA flow diagram shown below (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The PRISMA flow diagram.

3 Search Results

3.1 Number of Publications and Natural Disasters

The body of empirical evidence on the effects of climate change on NCDs is extensive and diverse, encompassing studies from various countries and examining a wide range of outcomes. Figure 2 illustrates the number of natural disasters and related academic publications from 1980 until 2023.¹ The publication count (red line) reflects the number of search results from the three searched databases: PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science. The first search result appears in the year 1981. Afterwards, the number of publications grows slowly at first but then accelerates sharply after 2000, reflecting a surge in academic interest likely driven by the growing recognition of climate change impacts and the increasing frequency of natural disasters.

This trend in academic publications parallels the increase in disasters shown by the grey line, which are sourced from the EM-DAT, a comprehensive global database that records and categorizes natural and technological disasters (Delforge et al. 2023).² These disasters have been filtered to include those relevant to our literature review: floods, droughts, storms, mass movements (dry and wet), wildfires, extreme temperatures, and

¹ For 2024, Scopus has recorded 145 results, PubMed 18 results, and Web of Science 3 results. The relatively lower counts for 2024 are likely due to the ongoing year and the fact that not all publications have been released or indexed yet (as of July 2024).

² Although the EM-DAT has some limitations, such as only reporting large disasters due to threshold criteria and potential geographical biases where coverage is limited, we use it to illustrate general descriptive trends rather than for detailed empirical analysis.

Figure 2: Annual number of publications (red), number of natural disasters (grey) and the 5-year moving average of the disasters (blue) from 1980 until 2023.

glacial lake outburst floods. The number of natural disasters shows an overall increase from 1980 to the 2000s, suggesting a link to climate change as extreme weather events become more frequent. The moving average (blue line) smooths out these fluctuations, highlighting a consistent upward trend over the decades.

After screening for relevance, our literature sample shows that most studies concentrate on North America, followed by Asia (see Figure A1 in the appendix). This focus may be due to the higher frequency of disasters in these regions as well as increased research interest in these regions.

Air pollution is the most frequently studied EWE category in our literature sample, followed by wildfires and droughts (see Figure A2 in the appendix). These three EWEs are often examined together, indicating their potential interrelation and combined impact. However, according to the data from the EM-DAT, the most common natural disasters are floods and storms (Delforge et al. 2023). This discrepancy may reflect a research focus on certain EWEs such as air pollution, wildfires, and droughts, which might not align with the broader distribution of natural disasters. Factors such as academic interest, data availability, or regional emphasis in the literature compared to the EM-DAT could contribute to this difference.

3.2 Measurements and Types of NCDs

In the screened literature, non-communicable diseases are medical conditions or diseases that are not infectious and cannot be transmitted from person to person.

They are typically long-lasting and progress slowly (World Health Organization 2023). NCDs cover a wide spectrum of chronic conditions, such as cardiovascular diseases, cancers, chronic respiratory diseases, diabetes, and mental health disorders, as well as neurologic, endocrine, gastrointestinal, renal, allergic, and autoimmune disorders.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), NCDs are responsible for 41 million deaths annually, representing 74 % of all deaths worldwide (World Health Organization 2023). **Cardiovascular diseases** (CVDs), the leading cause of NCD deaths, account for 17.9 million fatalities each year. These diseases include coronary artery disease, hypertension (high blood pressure), arrhythmia (irregular heartbeats), heart failure, and stroke. They often result from genetic predisposition and lifestyle factors such as poor diet, lack of physical activity, and smoking (World Health Organization 2023).

Cancers are the second leading cause of NCD deaths, claiming 9.3 million lives annually. They can affect any part of the body and are characterized by the uncontrolled growth of abnormal cells, with risk factors including genetics, lifestyle choices, and environmental exposures. For example, following an earthquake and tsunami, higher hospitalization rates were observed for the progression of lung cancer, among other respiratory diseases (Yamanda et al. 2013).

Chronic respiratory diseases, responsible for 4.1 million deaths each year, include conditions like chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma. These diseases can be exacerbated by environmental factors such as air pollution, smoking, and exposure to occupational hazards.

Diabetes results in 2.0 million deaths annually, including those from kidney disease caused by diabetes. This metabolic disorder, particularly type 2 diabetes, is characterized by high blood sugar levels due to insulin resistance or deficiency and is heavily influenced by diet, physical activity, and obesity. Natural disasters can exacerbate diabetes management due to increased stress levels, food insecurity, and malnutrition, all of which are associated with a higher incidence of diabetes and impaired glucose tolerance (Ngaruiya et al. 2022).

Mental health disorders encompass a wide range of conditions that affect mood, thinking, and behaviour, including depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, and schizophrenia. These disorders are influenced by genetics, environmental factors, trauma, and significant life changes. A subset of these conditions, referred to as Common Mental Disorders (CMD), includes non-psychotic disorders such as depression, anxiety disorders, phobias, and obsessive–compulsive disorder (Graham et al. 2019).

Collectively, these four major NCDs – cardiovascular diseases, cancers, chronic respiratory diseases, and diabetes – are responsible for over 80 % of all premature NCD deaths (World Health Organization 2023).

The **measurement** of NCDs is broadly categorized into mortality and hospital admissions. Mortality indicators include general mortality (total and all-cause

mortality), age-specific mortality, and cause-specific mortality. Hospital admissions indicators encompass all-cause hospitalizations, emergency department visits, excess hospital admissions, ambulance attendances, age-specific admissions, and cause-specific admissions (e.g. cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, including asthma and allergic diseases, as well as renal diseases and mental health conditions).

3.3 Inclusion of Socio-Economic Control Variables

In analysing the impact of climate change on NCDs, it is crucial to include socio-economic control variables, as these factors can significantly influence health outcomes and help account for confounding effects (Weilhammer et al. 2021). These control variables help to isolate the specific effects of extreme weather events on health outcomes. Studies find evidence that older people or socioeconomically deprived people are more vulnerable due to either existing health problems or inability to afford medical treatment (see Section 4.2).

Commonly used socio-economic control variables in these studies include **age**, as different age groups can have varying susceptibility to the health impacts of extreme weather events, and **gender**, since health impacts may differ between males and females, necessitating gender-specific analysis (Fouillet et al. 2006). Some studies use different age groups, some use the pension status of individuals (Caamano-Isorna et al. 2011).

Income level is another crucial variable, as socio-economic status often influences access to healthcare and overall vulnerability to health impacts (Lamond, Joseph, and Proverbs 2015). **Education** level is also commonly controlled for, given that higher education levels are generally associated with better health outcomes and greater awareness of health risks. **Employment** status can affect stress levels, access to healthcare, and overall health, making it an important variable. In some studies, the employment status is classified as either employed, unemployed or inactive (Graham et al. 2019). This approach can, however, contradict the Clean Control Condition, as EWEs often impact both income and employment levels. For instance, a flood may destroy income sources, which in turn affects NCDs through changes in socio-economic status. Thus, when including these variables, the direct impact of EWEs on NCDs might be underestimated, as the control variables themselves can obscure the full effect of the disasters (see Berlemann and Eurich 2022).

Additionally, the distinction between urban and rural **residence** is significant because the location of residence can influence exposure to extreme weather events and access to healthcare services.

Housing tenure can affect the extent of damage experienced and the capacity for recovery, which in turn impacts health. For instance, Graham et al. (2019) utilized

housing tenure as a control variable in their study on the effects of storms, categorizing participants as owner-occupiers (reference group), social renters, and private renters.

Alcohol consumption is a known risk factor for various NCDs, including cardiovascular diseases, liver disease, and certain cancers. Some studies therefore categorize participants into low/no risk (reference group), hazardous, and harmful drinkers (Graham et al. 2019). This categorization helps isolate the specific effects of alcohol consumption, ensuring that varying health risks associated with alcohol are adequately accounted for.

4 Indicators of Climate Change and Their Impact on NCDs

In most studies, extreme weather events serve as critical indicators of climate change and are essential in analysing its impacts on non-communicable diseases. Existing literature extensively examines the effects of individual extreme weather events or changes in specific climate variables on NCDs. In this review, we focus on heatwaves, wildfires and air pollution, floods, droughts as well as storms.

4.1 Heatwaves

Heatwaves are mostly defined as prolonged periods of excessively high temperatures. Various studies have employed different criteria to define heatwaves, often depending on the specific climate and population characteristics of the study regions. The definitions of heatwaves in the literature vary significantly, reflecting different criteria and thresholds used across studies. These can be grouped and classified into several main categories based on their defining characteristics (Table 1).

Percentile-based approaches, like using the 90th percentile of local temperatures, account for regional climate variability but may lack consistency across different areas. Absolute thresholds, such as defining heatwaves as temperatures above 35 °C, provide clear and comparable criteria but ignore local climate differences. Heat index methods, which factor in humidity, are more complex to calculate. Impact-based definitions, such as hospital admissions during heatwaves, directly link heat to health outcomes but may not capture the full range of effects on non-communicable diseases like cardiovascular or respiratory conditions. Table 1 provides an overview of the different definitions of heatwaves, their characteristics, and some associated references.

Table 1: Definitions of heatwaves in the literature.

Definition	Description	References
Percentile-based	Thresholds set relative to historical temperature distributions, considering local climate variations.	Chen et al. (2015); Ma et al. (2015); Revich and Shaposhnikov (2008); Son, Bell, and Lee (2014); Zeng et al. (2014)
Absolute temperature thresholds	Definitions based on fixed temperature thresholds, enabling consistent criteria across different regions.	Hertel et al. (2009); Huang, Kan, and Kovats (2010); Huynen et al. (2001); Sun et al. (2014); Turner, Connell, and Tong (2013); Yang et al. (2013)
Heat index and apparent temperature	Consideration of perceived temperatures, including both heat and humidity, for a more accurate representation of human exposure.	D'Ippoliti et al. (2010); Gronlund et al. (2014); Mastrangelo et al. (2007); Monteiro et al. (2013)
Climatological periods and variability	Use of specific periods identified through climatological analysis or temperature variability to account for prolonged heat exposure.	Conti et al. (2007); Fouillet et al. (2006); Knowlton et al. (2008); Rocklöv and Forsberg (2009)
Impact-based	Definitions based on observed health outcomes, focussing on real-world effects rather than temperature alone.	Anderson et al. (2013); Kovats, Hajat, and Wilkinson (2004); Lin et al. (2013); Stafoggia et al. (2006)

Overall, we identify 37 papers which examine the impact of heat and rising temperatures on both mortality and morbidity related to NCDs. Twenty five of them report results on mortality, 16 on morbidity and 4 analyse both outcomes.

4.1.1 Impact on mortality

Heatwaves appear to have a significant impact on NCDs, as suggested by numerous studies conducted in various regions and among different populations (Table 2). Results from the reviewed studies were classified as significant or insignificant based on whether the authors explicitly stated the level of significance in their papers or if the results were marked as significant in the tables provided (see note below Table 2 for an explanation of the effect size symbols). In cases where outcomes across multiple locations (e.g. cities) were investigated and (1) not all or the majority of results were significant, (2) significant results showed conflicting directions (e.g. increase or decrease), or (3) different statistical methods led to varying results, the findings were classified as inconclusive.

Out of 29 studies analysed, 25 found significant increases in all-cause mortality associated with heatwaves (Baccini et al. 2008; Conti et al. 2007; Fouillet et al. 2006; Monteiro et al. 2013, among others). Cardiovascular mortality was also substantially affected, with 19 studies reporting significant increases (e.g. Baccini et al. 2008;

Table 2: Impact of heat on mortality.

Outcome	Direction	Significance	Reference
Mortality			
All-cause	Increase	Significant	+++ Fouillet et al. (2006); +++ Monteiro et al. (2013); ++ Baccini et al. (2008); ++ Conti et al. (2007) ^b ; ++ Hertel et al. (2009); ++ Royé et al. (2020); ++ Stafoggia et al. (2006); + Analitis et al. (2014); + Bi et al. (2022); + Chen et al. (2015); + D'Ippoliti et al. (2010) ^a ; + Huynen et al. (2001); + Huang, Kan, and Kovats (2010); + Kovats, Hajat, and Wilkinson (2004); + Lin et al. (2013); + Revich and Shaposhnikov (2008); + Schulte, Rössli, and Ragettli (2021); + Sun et al. (2014); + Barnett et al. (2012); Cheng et al. (2024); Cvetinovic, Zorica Podražčanin, and Tatjana (2019); Ma et al. (2015); Sheridan and Lin (2014); Yang et al. (2013); Zeng et al. (2014)
Cardiovascular	Increase	Significant	++ Baccini et al. (2008); ++ Chen et al. (2015); ++ Fouillet et al. (2006); ++ Miron et al. (2015); ++ Royé et al. (2020); ++ Schulte, Rössli, and Ragettli (2021); ++ Yang et al. (2013); + Analitis et al. (2014); + Bi et al. (2022); + D'Ippoliti et al. (2010); + Huang, Kan, and Kovats (2010); + Lin et al. (2013); + Sun et al. (2014); Arisco et al. (2023); Cheng et al. (2024); Huynen et al. (2001); Khatana, Werner, and Groeneveld (2022); Ma et al. (2015); Sheridan and Lin (2014)
		Insignificant	Hertel et al. (2009)
– Stroke	Increase	Significant	+++ Chen et al. (2015); + Huang, Kan, and Kovats (2010); ++ Schulte, Rössli, and Ragettli (2021)
– IHD	Increase	Significant	+++ Chen et al. (2015); + Revich and Shaposhnikov (2008)
– MI	Increase	Significant	Schulte, Rössli, and Ragettli (2021); Zanolibetti et al. (2012)
– Heart failure	Increase	Significant	+ Schulte, Rössli, and Ragettli (2021); Zanolibetti et al. (2012)
– CHD	Increase	Significant	Huang, Kan, and Kovats (2010)
– Arrhythmia	Increase	Significant	++ Schulte, Rössli, and Ragettli (2021)
– Hypertension	Increase	Significant	++ Schulte, Rössli, and Ragettli (2021)
Respiratory	Increase	Significant	+++ Baccini et al. (2008); +++ Fouillet et al. (2006); +++ Hertel et al. (2009); +++ Revich and Shaposhnikov (2008); ++ Analitis et al. (2014); ++ Chen et al. (2015); ++ D'Ippoliti et al. (2010) ^a ; ++ Royé et al. (2020); ++ Yang et al. (2013); + Bi et al. (2022); + Cheng et al. (2024); + Huang, Kan, and Kovats (2010); + Huynen et al. (2001); + Miron et al. (2015); + Sun et al. (2014); Ma et al. (2015); Sheridan and Lin (2014)
		Insignificant	Arisco et al. (2023)
		Inconclusive	Lin et al. (2013)
– COPD	Increase	Significant	++ Chen et al. (2015); Zanolibetti et al. (2012)
		Insignificant	Huang, Kan, and Kovats (2010)
– ARI		Insignificant	Huang, Kan, and Kovats (2010)

Table 2: (continued)

Outcome	Direction	Significance	Reference
Cerebrovascular	Increase	Significant	++ D'Ippoliti et al. (2010) ^a ; + Revich and Shaposhnikov (2008); Ma et al. (2015)
		Insignificant	Analitis et al. (2014)
Neoplasm	Increase	Significant	Fouillet et al. (2006); Huynen et al. (2001)
		Insignificant	Hertel et al. (2009)

Note: IHD, Ischaemic Heart Disease; MI, Myocardial Infarction; CHD, Congenital Heart Defect; COPD, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease; ARI, Acute Respiratory Infection. Statistical significance is defined by a 95 % confidence interval (CI). + An increase of 10–25 %; ++ An increase of 25–50 %; +++ An increase of ≥ 50 %. ^aFor individuals ≥ 65 years; ^bFor individuals ≥ 75 years.

Chen et al. 2015; Fouillet et al. 2006; Schulte, Rösli, and Ragetti 2021), and respiratory outcomes were significantly impacted in 17 studies (e.g. Baccini et al. 2008; Fouillet et al. 2006; Revich and Shaposhnikov 2008). In addition, heatwaves were found to have varying effects on specific diseases within these two categories. For instance, **stroke**-related mortality showed significant increases in three studies (Chen et al. 2015; Huang, Kan, and Kovats 2010; Schulte, Rösli, and Ragetti 2021), while mortality due to **ischaemic heart disease** (IHD) was also elevated (Chen et al. 2015; Revich and Shaposhnikov 2008).

Similarly, **respiratory** diseases such as **COPD** were particularly vulnerable to heat, with multiple studies reporting significant increases in mortality (Chen et al. 2015; Zanobetti et al. 2012). While evidence on cardiovascular mortality is mostly conclusive, some studies report inconclusive or insignificant results for respiratory, cerebrovascular disease and neoplasm (e.g. Analitis et al. 2014; Hertel et al. 2009; Huang, Kan, and Kovats 2010).

In summary, the reviewed studies overwhelmingly show that extreme heat and rising temperatures are associated with increased mortality, particularly from cardiovascular, respiratory, and all-cause outcomes. The evidence emphasizes the heightened vulnerability of certain groups, including the elderly and those with existing NCDs, to the impacts of extreme temperatures.

4.1.2 Impact on morbidity

When examining the impact of heat, heatwaves, and higher temperatures on NCDs, most studies found significant increases in morbidity, as measured by hospitalizations, emergency department visits or need for medical assistance (Table 3). For instance, **morbidity** (measured as hospital admissions) was reported to significantly increase due to heat exposure in studies by Gronlund et al. (2014), and Knowlton et al. (2008), with some showing strong effects (Turner, Connell, and Tong 2013). However, studies

Table 3: Impact of heat on morbidity (hospitalizations, emergency department visits).

Outcome	Direction	Significance	Reference	
Morbidity				
All-cause	Increase	Significant	+++ Turner, Connell, and Tong (2013); Gronlund et al. (2014); Knowlton et al. (2008); Ma et al. (2011)	
	Decrease	Significant	Schulte, Rööslü, and Ragettli (2021)	
		Insignificant	Kovats, Hajat, and Wilkinson (2004); Schneider, Thieken, and Walz (2023)	
Cardiovascular	Increase	Inconclusive	Guirguis et al. (2018); Rocklöv and Forsberg (2009)	
		Significant	++ Turner, Connell, and Tong (2013); + Mastrangelo et al. (2007) ^b ; + Schneider, Thieken, and Walz (2023); Knowlton et al. (2008); Ma et al. (2011); Monteiro et al. (2013); Son, Bell, and Lee (2014)	
		Insignificant	– Schulte, Rööslü, and Ragettli (2021)	
	Decrease	Significant	Giang et al. (2014); Gronlund et al. (2014) ^a ; Guirguis et al. (2018); Kovats, Hajat, and Wilkinson (2004); Lim, Hong, and Kim (2012); Michelozzi et al. (2009); Ponjoan et al. (2017); Sheridan and Lin (2014)	
		Inconclusive	Rocklöv and Forsberg (2009)	
	– Stroke	Insignificant	Lim, Hong, and Kim 2012; Schulte, Rööslü, and Ragettli 2021	
	– IHD		Inconclusive	Lim, Hong, and Kim (2012)
	– MI	Decrease	Significant	– Schulte, Rööslü, and Ragettli (2021); Knowlton et al. (2008)
	– Cardiac failure	Increase	Insignificant	Lim, Hong, and Kim (2012)
			Significant	+ Lim, Hong, and Kim (2012)
– Cardiac disease	Decrease	Significant	-- Monteiro et al. (2013); Schulte, Rööslü, and Ragettli (2021); Hopp, Dominici, and Bobb (2018) ^a	
	– Arrhythmia	Inconclusive	Lim, Hong, and Kim (2012)	
		Insignificant	Schulte, Rööslü, and Ragettli (2021)	
– Hypertension	–	Inconclusive	Lim, Hong, and Kim (2012)	
Respiratory	Increase	Significant	+++ Turner, Connell, and Tong (2013); ++ Michelozzi et al. (2009); ++ Monteiro et al. (2013); + Lim, Hong, and Kim (2012); + Mastrangelo et al. (2007) ^b ; Anderson et al. (2013); Gronlund et al. (2014) ^a ; Knowlton et al. (2008); Kovats, Hajat, and Wilkinson (2004); Ma et al. (2011); Sheridan and Lin (2014); Son, Bell, and Lee (2014)	
		Insignificant	Schneider, Thieken, and Walz (2023)	
		Inconclusive	Guirguis et al. (2018); Rocklöv and Forsberg (2009)	
	– COPD	Increase	Significant	++ Monteiro et al. (2013); Anderson et al. (2013)
			Inconclusive	Lim, Hong, and Kim (2012)
	– ARI		Insignificant	Anderson et al. (2013)
	– Asthma	Increase	Significant	+ Lim, Hong, and Kim (2012); Son, Bell, and Lee (2014)
	– Allergic disease	Increase	Significant	Son, Bell, and Lee (2014)

Table 3: (continued)

Outcome	Direction	Significance	Reference
Cerebrovascular	Decrease	Significant	Knowlton et al. (2008)
		Insignificant	Michelozzi et al. (2009); Monteiro et al. (2013)
Renal disease	Increase	Significant	+ Gronlund et al. (2014) ^a ; + Hopp, Dominici, and Bobb (2018) ^a ; + Knowlton et al. (2008); Guirguis et al. (2018); Kovats, Hajat, and Wilkinson (2004)
Mental health	Increase	Significant	Bundo et al. (2021)
		Insignificant	Guirguis et al. (2018)
Heat-related disease ⁵	Increase	Significant	+++ Guirguis et al. (2018); +++ Hopp, Dominici, and Bobb (2018) ^a ; +++ Knowlton et al. (2008)

Note: MI, Myocardial Infarction; COPD, Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease; ARI, Acute Respiratory Infection. Statistical significance is defined by a 95 % confidence interval (CI). +/- An increase of 10–25 %; +/+ An increase of 25–50 %; +++/- An increase of ≥ 50 %. ^aFor individuals ≥ 65 years; ^bFor individuals ≥ 75 years. ⁵Illnesses related to ICD-9-CM Code 992 (e.g., heat exhaustion, heat fatigue, heat edema, etc.).

like Schulte, Rösli, and Ragetti (2021) noted decreases in morbidity, and others like Kovats, Hajat, and Wilkinson (2004) found insignificant changes in all-cause hospital admissions but significant increase in respiratory morbidity. Rocklöv and Forsberg (2009) categorized morbidity outcomes as inconclusive, indicating that varying methods yield different results.

In total, 20 papers are included in our review focussing on the impact of heat and rising temperatures on morbidity. Four of them show a significant increase in all-cause morbidity, 7 report a significant increase in cardiovascular diseases while 8 provide insignificant results. For respiratory disease, we find 12 significant results in the screened literature.

Heat-related diseases, such as heat exhaustion or heat fatigue, were shown to strongly increase NCDs (+++) across multiple studies, with various authors finding severe effects.

Significant increases in **cardiovascular** morbidity were found in studies such as Turner, Connell, and Tong (2013) and Mastrangelo et al. (2007), with strong effects (++) across multiple populations. Nevertheless, Schulte, Rösli, and Ragetti (2021) reported decreases in cardiovascular emergency hospital admissions, while research by Gronlund et al. (2014) and Michelozzi et al. (2009) found no significant effects. The decrease in cardiovascular emergency hospital admissions may be due to heat causing people to sweat more and their blood vessels to widen, which reduces the strain on the heart (Schulte, Rösli, and Ragetti 2021). This lowers blood pressure and improves the condition of patients with heart failure, similar to the effects of medications that specifically target heart function. Moreover, Rocklöv and Forsberg (2009) again classified their results as inconclusive due to conflicting results in the data.

Respiratory outcomes, on the other hand, exhibited a more consistent pattern of deterioration, particularly in relation to heat exposure. Strong effects (+++) were found in studies like Turner, Connell, and Tong (2013) and Monteiro et al. (2013) for conditions such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Studies by Mastrangelo et al. (2007) and Anderson et al. (2013) further confirmed these findings, although some studies reported inconclusive outcomes for specific respiratory conditions like acute respiratory infections (ARI) (Anderson et al. 2013).

The impact of high temperatures and heat on **mental health** appears rather inconclusive. Studies like Bundo et al. (2021) report increases in mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, and stress during heat events. In contrast, Guirguis et al. (2018) report insignificant results in their study focussing on different climate regions of San Diego County in the United States.

In conclusion, most findings consistently point toward a significant increase in morbidity – especially for respiratory conditions and heat-related diseases – as a result of heat exposure.

4.2 Wildfires and Air Pollution

Wildfires, which are often intensified by extreme heat, not only further raise temperatures but also release harmful pollutants into the air, compounding the health risks associated with heatwaves. The channels through which they affect human health also include air, water, and land pollution. This section highlights the literature on the relationship between air pollution due to wildfires and human health based on their corresponding focus-areas:

- Wildfire smoke affects human health significantly through air pollution.
- Socioeconomically deprived populations are more vulnerable than other segments of the population.
- Air pollution due to wildfires exacerbates existing illnesses.
- Impact depends on the topography and inhabitation.
- Anthropogenic intervention like deforestation aggravates wildfires.

Wildfire smoke affects human health significantly through air pollution. This smoke contains particulate matter and poisonous substances causing respiratory, cardiovascular, ophthalmologic and mental health problems (Wollschlaeger et al. 2022). The main cause can be attributed to high blood pressure that distorts heart rhythm resulting in increased hypertension, heart attacks, or ischaemic heart issues. Additionally, wildfire smoke can exacerbate gastrointestinal diseases, allergies, asthma or related issues, as well as cancers such as breast and lung cancer. These effects are heterogenous amongst the population based on sociodemographic characteristics given similar levels

of exposure to the events (Finlay et al. 2012). Numerous studies show that the most significant channel of impact is through air pollution, with respiratory morbidity and mental illnesses being the most prominent NCDs (Liu et al. 2015; Sheehan 2022). Wildfire smoke also leads to increased cognitive impairment like Dementia and Alzheimer as well as mental health issues like anxiety (Wollschlaeger et al. 2022). These effects are more pronounced for people with existing cognitive issues, people under psychiatric medications as well as for people who are highly concerned about mental well-being.

Furthermore, people exposed to a wildfire in Californian region were found to be using increased psychotropic medication, suggesting a higher level of mental health problems (Wettstein and Vaidyanathan 2024). Evidence suggests that health issues related to air pollution constitute a significant proportion of total health issues. This is supported by the notable proportion of literature related to air pollution compared to the total literature in our sample literature collection (see Figure A1). For example, due to wildfire smoke, chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases account for 50 % and ischaemic heart diseases account for 25 % of the total disease burden (Frumkin and Haines 2019). These effects are predicted to increase significantly in the future. A study based on the wildlife smoke exposure and either hospitalisation or emergency visits during the period 2003–2010 in the western USA, estimated the impact of future increases in wildfires on potential health outcomes in the year 2050 (Stowell et al. 2022). Some studies find evidence that decrease in air pollution levels to a reduction in respiratory and cardiovascular diseases (Breitner-Busch et al. 2023; Hwang et al. 2023). This evidence is crucial for understanding the counterfactual and causal links when it comes to wildfire smoke exposure and health outcomes: it shows not only that an increase in air pollution is associated with an increase in NCDs but also demonstrates that a decrease in air pollution is linked to a reduction in NCDs.

Studies find that socioeconomically deprived populations are more vulnerable than other segments of the population. For example, a study on the October 2007 wildfires in Southern California as a natural experiment explores the heterogenous impact of wildfire smoke on both sides of the San Diego-Tijuana border based on corresponding cardio-respiratory hospitalizations (Schwarz et al. 2023). It finds that Tijuana has lesser hospitalization rates than San Diego and attributes this difference in rate across the border to socioeconomic characteristics, such as the poverty rate, which in Tijuana is three times more than that of San Diego.

Another study finds that the effects are heterogenous across age groups, where the greatest share of affected are children younger than 5 years and individuals older than 65 years (Heaney et al. 2022). It also finds that smoke increases respiratory diseases by 3 %, where 10 % of the 3 % increase is due to asthma. Not only across age groups but also across gender is the effect heterogenous due to the extent of exposure to the smoke. For example, a study on the August 2006 wildfires in Galicia, Spain, finds increased drug use

for obstructive airway diseases among pensioners and a significant rise in anxiolytic-hypnotic use among men in fire-affected areas (Caamano-Isorna et al. 2011).

Air pollution due to wildfires also causes diseases healthy population. A study on the wave of fires in November 2016 in Israel finds that individuals of low socio-economic status without existing illnesses were at greater risk of experiencing long-term effects following fires, that was evident from persistently higher hospitalization rates for 2 years post event (Cohen, Shapira, and Furman 2022). These effects could be categorized into two effects viz. short-term and long-term (Breitner-Busch et al. 2023). It shows that the short-term manifests from short duration exposure to increase in fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) that leads to increase in the risk of acute cardiovascular events by 1–3 %. The long-term effect from prolonged exposure over time that increases the risk of acute cardiovascular events by 10 % due to the onset or aggravation of hypertension and diabetes.

Some studies find that air pollution due to wildfires exacerbates existing illnesses. Its exposure increases oxidative stress and inflammation, individuals with pre-existing cardiovascular conditions may experience increased illness during and after wildfire events (Cascio 2018). Similar effects are found by another study on the wave of fires in November 2016 in Israel already discussed earlier. It finds that people with underlying morbidity are at greater risk of experiencing long-term effects following fires (Cohen, Shapira, and Furman 2022). The reason of these effects could be that beyond a certain threshold of pollutants is exceeded during wildfires, respiratory hospitalizations and emergency visits (ED) due to asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease increase (Reid et al. 2019). One study explains this threshold effect by exploring various wildfires in Greece to estimate differences in particle toxicity or deposition location in the human respiratory tract (RT) on the oxidative potential (OP) exposure (Mylonaki et al. 2024). It finds that air pollutants have significant OP, which implies reduction in level of antioxidants in body, resulting in exacerbation of cardiovascular and respiratory illnesses.

The effects of air pollution from wildfire are also heterogenous based on the topography and inhabitation around the wildfire events. For example, emissions like poisonous gases and harmful particulate matter from wildfires that impact human health are influenced by factors like the type of vegetation, fire characteristics, landscape and weather conditions (Cascio 2018). A study finds no relationship for the overall sample between PM_{2.5} content and respiratory or circulatory disease-related hospital emergency visits or mortality between 2013 and 2018 in California's Shasta county (Casey et al. 2021). However, it finds that in sub-local regions with lower elevation, dense population, generally poor air quality areas, PM_{2.5} is associated with 15 % increase in respiratory disease-related hospital visits in the same week.

The final type of literature delves into wildfires caused by anthropogenic intervention and its effects on human health. Our search result found only one

literature that examines the association between deforestation-induced fires and respiratory health issues (Ribeiro et al. 2024). It finds that deforestation leads to arid conditions, higher temperatures, and lower precipitation that leads to wildfires and shows higher hospitalisation rates in Brazil's Amazon region during the forest fire season between 2009 and 2019. Another study on exceptionally intense global wildfire events using 21 years of satellite data shows that the frequency of extreme wildfires has increased 2.2 times from 2003 to 2023, with 6 of the most extreme events occurring in the past 7 years (Cunningham, Williamson, and Bowman 2024). Studies like above are very few and need to be extended to other EWEs to examine the causal linkage between climate change, EWEs and their impact on NCDs.

In conclusion, although some studies find mixed effects which could be attributed either to their research design or data, most of the studies find significant effects of wildfires through air pollution on human respiratory, cardiovascular and mental health. Most of the studies report significant impacts on physiological illnesses and very few of them focus on mental illnesses. Morbidity and mortality due to asthma, hypertension, diabetes increase, which is identified through increased hospitalisation rates, increase in medicinal drugs consumption as well as reporting of aggravation of existing diseases. Similar effects are also found for mental illnesses which provides evidence of wildlife fires and air pollution on mental health. The effects are also heterogenous across different ages, sociodemographic factors, and topographies. For example, older and younger people are more vulnerable, financially weak people are unable to avail treatment due to higher treatment costs. This bolsters the deployment of socioeconomic variables like age, education, employment, gender etc. in the empirical analysis.

Finally, deforestation is shown to lead towards drier weather, lesser rainfall, higher temperatures and increased wildfires. Few studies focus on establishing linkage between either climate change or anthropogenic activities and wildfire or air pollution. Most of them consider climate change as a premise to wildfires without providing adequate empirical evidence. However, there are also studies which show the effects of wildfires without positing climate change as given. This is a substantial gap which would serve as a significant contribution to existing literature by linking climate change and human health (non-communicable diseases, mental health) through extreme weather events like wildfires. The next Section 4.3 discusses the effect of floods on human health.

4.3 Floods

4.3.1 Anxiety and Trauma

Flooding can have significant long-term psychological effects, particularly in communities that experience repeated flooding. The distress and trauma associated with flood damage

Table 4: Effect of floods on mental health in Lamond et al. (2015).

Outcome	Effect size
Anxiety	Very strong
Flashbacks	Moderate
Nightmares	Weak
Sleeplessness, depression	Moderate
Stress, anger, relationship tension, loss of concentration, need to visit the doctor, alcohol use	Moderate

and losses can lead to lasting mental health disorders, which can undermine the community's resilience to future flooding events.

A review study by Lamond, Joseph, and Proverbs (2015) illustrates the wide range of measured impacts of flooding on mental health, showing that between 8.6 % and 53 % of the population in countries such as Korea, England, China, and Thailand exhibit symptoms of psychological nature such as Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety, or depression. In Table 4, the effect sizes of various outcomes are displayed, indicating that anxiety has a very strong effect, with over 60 % of respondents reporting frequent anxiety during rainfall, even long after the flood event.

Frequent flashbacks were reported by 23 % of households as occurring “always” or “very often”, while nearly two-thirds experienced them, albeit rarely. Nightmares were less prevalent, with 60 % of respondents never experiencing them and fewer than 10 % reporting them as occurring “always” or “very often”. Sleeplessness and depression showed similar patterns, with 18 % of respondents experiencing these issues “always” or “very often”. Consequently, flashbacks, sleeplessness, and depression are associated with a moderate effect size, while nightmares are categorized as having a weak effect size. Additionally, stress, anger, relationship tension, loss of concentration, increased need to visit the doctor, and alcohol use are identified as having a moderate effect size. Notably, studies conducted shortly after a flood event tend to report higher rates of mental health disorders compared to those conducted later, although symptoms can persist in some individuals for many years. Additionally, the study reveals that minor psychosocial impacts are less frequently measured or reported compared to more severe disorders.

Moreover, the study by Lamond, Joseph, and Proverbs (2015) empirically investigates the long-term psychological effects of the 2007 flood event in England using a postal survey of affected households. The authors found that household income, the depth of flooding, the need to relocate during restoration, as well as mitigation actions were related to the prevalence of stress, anxiety, depression, and mental health deterioration. Relocation and household income were the most predictive factors for psychological distress.

In addition, these mental health effects of flooding extend beyond immediate trauma and can persist for years (Charlson et al. 2021). In line with the findings from Lamond, Joseph, and Proverbs (2015), a study by Charlson et al. (2021) shows that the threat of flooding significantly contributes to a decline in well-being. This decline is particularly pronounced in rural communities, where the interplay between these climatic stressors exacerbates mental health challenges. Moreover, their research indicates that psychological morbidity, such as symptoms of depression and anxiety, can continue for at least 3 years after a flooding event. Additionally, the study points out that perceived risks associated with climate change further contribute to psychological distress, as individuals grapple with the anticipation and uncertainty of future climate-related threats.

Consistent with previous findings, Dai et al. (2017) observe that PTSD and anxiety were prevalent among survivors of the 1998 Dongting Lake flood in China, with rates of 9.5 % and 9.2 %, respectively. Although these figures align with the general pattern of persistent mental health issues observed in flood survivors, they are notably lower compared to the higher prevalence rates reported in studies examining the immediate aftermath of other major flooding events.

On the contrary, Mulchandani et al. (2020) report a decrease in the prevalence of depression, anxiety, and PTSD following a flood. Their study found that depression rates dropped from 20.8 % in the first year to 7.8 % by the third year, anxiety from 27.6 % to 11.8 %, and PTSD from 33.2 % to 17.1 %. However, mental illness rates remained higher compared to the period before the flood, which is in line with previous findings.

4.3.2 Risk Factors

Different studies yield varying findings on the risk factors for developing mental illness following disasters. These risk factors encompass several variables, including: the severity of the traumatic event, exposure to the injury or death of a loved one, gender, age, socioeconomic status, educational level, minority or ethnic background, psychiatric history, family instability, and insufficient social support (Palinkas and Wong 2020). For instance, Dai et al. (2017) identified that low social support and traits of emotional instability were significant risk factors for PTSD among disaster survivors, with females being particularly vulnerable to such psychiatric disorders. However, their study did not identify significant associations between PTSD or anxiety and other factors such as age, educational level, or marital status, which have been reported as risk factors in other research. Individuals in low- and middle-income countries are especially susceptible due to their heightened exposure to

extreme weather events, greater levels of poverty, and limited access to essential services (Cianconi, Betrò, and Janiri 2020).

4.3.3 Drowning, Physical Injuries, and Contamination

Expanding on these insights, a review by Agache et al. (2022) identifies drowning as the leading cause of death during floods, with flash floods exacerbating this risk. Immediate health threats also include trauma, musculoskeletal injuries, wounds, and carbon monoxide poisoning from unventilated generators. Additionally, floods contribute to indirect health issues through damage to healthcare infrastructure and exposure to contaminants.

The review highlights the risks of water contamination, which can lead to increased mortality, loss of potable water, and increased spread of vector-borne and waterborne diseases. The aftermath of Hurricane Katrina is cited as an example, with residents exposed to pollutants and pathogens such as hydrocarbon fuels and heavy metals (Agache et al. 2022).

Similarly, Weilhhammer et al. (2021) emphasize the increased risks of disease outbreaks related to flooding. Their review highlights the increased risks of waterborne and foodborne diseases, including gastrointestinal illnesses. While these infectious conditions are important health concerns, they fall outside the primary scope of NCDs.

In conclusion, the impact of flooding on NCDs is significant, encompassing both psychological and physical health dimensions. The long-term psychological effects of flooding, particularly in areas with recurrent events, manifest as persistent mental health disorders such as PTSD, anxiety, and depression. While some studies indicate a decrease in these conditions over time, mental health issues often remain elevated compared to pre-flood levels.

4.4 Droughts

Documenting the impacts of drought is challenging due to the slow onset of the phenomenon and the complex nature of its effects. The difficulty lies in measuring and defining drought due to its gradual development, lack of highly visible impacts, and ability to affect large areas across geopolitical boundaries. Various indicators are used to measure the onset, duration, and extent, which leads to diverse definitions and a lack of standardization. Generally, drought is defined as a prolonged period of abnormally dry weather, resulting in a significant water deficit compared to a regional

norm (Stanke et al. 2013). It can lead to serious hydrological imbalances and is characterized by a deficiency in water supply due to consistently below-average precipitation.

Standard quantitative indices of drought measurements are deployed to monitor and evaluate droughts (NCEI 2024). One study considered a variety of such indices to analyse effects of drought in USA (Gwon et al. 2024). It finds that 6-month exposure duration witnessed higher risk of cardiovascular mortality as compared to 12-month exposure duration. We consider one potential cause as the timing and intensity of accompanying heatwave and air pollution in the short term as well as the duration for which the drought persisted with highest intensity. These factors are not well explained in this study. Furthermore, they are not well researched using adequate research designs. They also find the higher levels of mortality for both older male and female population. Furthermore, white populations show statistically significant effect on general mortality, however other race population showed statistically insignificant effects. Studies have found that Australian women's mental health appears less affected by droughts compared to men. This difference is attributed to the lack of consideration for occupational differences between genders in the research (Vins et al. 2015). This encourages to delve more into sociodemographic heterogeneity effects due to race as well as exposure duration.

A systematic literature review highlights the mechanisms through which droughts contribute to NCDs (Salvador et al. 2023). It posits that droughts lead to arid and drier environment that causes dust air pollution and wildfires. Similar to the effects of heatwaves and air pollution as discussed in Section 4.1 and Section 4.2, respectively, droughts lead to mental stress due to food scarcity. One systematic literature review finds an increase of 3.1 % in the level of distress or occupational stress in farmers due to a higher need for psychological resilience during drought affecting their production in USA as compared to non-drought conditions (Sheehan 2022). These effects are more pronounced in rural regions than urban regions due to higher prevalence of farming activities and greater reliance of the rural populations on agricultural output for their livelihood or income (Sullenbarger, Schutzenhofer, and Haase 2022). It is also found that affluent counties in Australia have better mental health conditions during drought as compared to less affluent counties due to better resilience (Vins et al. 2015). Furthermore, cultivation in drought prone areas is sustained by increased deployment of chemical fertilisers, which may have potential effects on mental health disorders, though this aspect is not covered in the literature.

Another systematic literature review on droughts in Australia finds that on average, the overall population is 26 % more likely to experience psychological problems during a drought compared to a non-drought situation (Walinski et al. 2023). Furthermore, the review finds studies that show that although children and adolescents in

drought-affected areas report higher levels of emotional distress compared to a normal sample, the difference is not statistically significant. Similarly, there is no significant difference in emotional distress between children living on farms and those in rural regions. This could either be due to the type of research design or absorption of stress by adults and having no spillovers to children and adolescents, which demands further exploration of the results based on heterogeneity in age as well as occupation classes.

When a drought is followed by a heatwave or increased air pollution, cardiovascular or respiratory diseases are reported. Urban areas are at higher risk of such diseases during drought periods due to pre-existing higher traffic-related air pollution and trapped urban heat (Salvador et al. 2023). A systematic literature review in Spain finds two related studies (Weilhammer et al. 2021). The first study conducted in Galicia, Spain finds higher levels of cardiovascular and respiratory mortality rates in interior regions compared to coastal regions, attributed to a relative cooling effect and moisture from sea proximity (Salvador et al. 2019). This shows that drier and arid regions exhibit higher mortality levels during drought periods. The study finds worsening drought increases the risk of respiratory mortality (11 %) more than that of cardiovascular mortality (6.4 %). The second study that covers the entire Spanish region found no overall effect between either respiratory or cardiovascular mortality and droughts (Salvador et al. 2020). However, it finds that urban provinces such as Madrid and Barcelona experience significantly higher mortality rates during drought periods due to cardiovascular and respiratory issues compared to rural provinces, which can be attributed to factors like population density, environmental pollution, and healthcare disparities.

Another study examining children under 5 years of age in the municipalities in Brazil's Amazon region affected by drought during the year 2005 finds a significant increase in hospitalisation rates due to respiratory diseases from aerosol exposure (Smith et al. 2014). During the 2005 drought, 31.3 % (77) of the affected municipalities saw hospitalizations increase from 1.3 % to 180 % compared to the 10-year mean. In another drought in 2010, 43.0 % (197) of municipalities experienced hospitalization increases ranging from 1.2 % to 267 %. The increase in hospitalizations during the 2010 drought was both more widespread and severe compared to 2005. Aerosols were a more significant factor in the 2005 drought than in 2010, despite the latter's larger spatial extent. This indicates that the concentration and distribution of aerosols, rather than the total drought area, may have a more pronounced impact on respiratory diseases. In areas severely affected by rainfall shortages, aerosol remained the key driver of respiratory diseases.

Not only do arid regions suffer from drought, but also water abundant countries like Canada can face them with dire consequences alike other drought prone countries (Yusa et al. 2015). One reason is that 98 % of the Canadian population lives in regions holding 38 % of the volume of Canada's freshwater resources. Additionally, general warming

trends are leading to changes in freshwater volume throughout the year, including intermittent dry periods with little to no rainfall. While the extent of drought-induced NCDs in Canada is not yet as critical as in more drought-prone countries, the potential for future health impacts should be a reason for concern.

In conclusion, due to the slow and pervasive nature of droughts, mental stress persists for a longer duration as compared to other forms of extreme weather events. As a major aspect of drought deals with water scarcity, rural regions are the forefront and worst to get affected. Correspondingly, in terms of occupation, farmers and the allied supply chain related to food and nutrition incurs market failure. This is a good avenue for economists to develop adequate incentives and correct inadequacies during times of drought for a more resilient society. Furthermore, some studies show no evidence for effect on women due to less focus on heterogeneity in gender-based occupation. This encourages detailed evaluation of the role of causal channels due to occupation. The studies have a global coverage from USA and Canada to Africa, from affluent to underdeveloped countries, which in purview of the present trend of growing drought cases would provide ample number of good comparison regions. Finally, drought leads to wildfires, which in turn leads to other events like heatwaves and air pollution and demands exploration of the effects on health through detailed integrated assessment models.

4.5 Storms

The occurrence of storms, especially in the form of cyclones with massive destructive power, is closely connected to climatic factors (Keller, DeVecchio, and Blodgett 2019). The impact of these storms on humans depends significantly on factors such as cyclone intensity, local population density, socioeconomic status and governance. Although the frequency of tropical cyclones is expected to decrease, the anticipated rise in both population density and cyclone intensity over the next two decades will likely lead to a significant increase in the number of people exposed annually, intensifying disaster risk, even with potential improvements in development and governance (Peduzzi et al. 2012).

While the relationship between climatic factors and the occurrence of storms is complex, there is evidence that both tropical and extratropical storm severity (wind speed, rainfall rates, etc.) may increase due to climate change (Bender et al. 2010). Additionally, global warming is likely to impact the regions where storms occur, potentially shifting their geographical distribution (Rummukainen 2012). Understanding these shifts is crucial, as changes in storm patterns have significant implications for non-communicable diseases. The disruption caused by storms can lead to exacerbations of cardiovascular and respiratory conditions due to physical

stress, displacement, and exposure to pollutants, which are discussed in detail hereafter.

Effect of storms depends on its type and the mechanism through which it affects NCDs. Walinski et al. (2023) focus on hurricane studies in USA on psychological disorders. They find that hurricanes not only increase anxiety in mentally healthy individuals but are also persistent for up to 12 years post exposure to hurricanes. They also find that due to destruction of healthcare infrastructure during hurricanes, mental health treatment completion rates dropped to half, leading to higher mental health patients. This phenomenon is more prevalent in adolescent and young adults with more traumatic exposures during hurricanes. All the above effects are attributed by the authors to presence of injuries or death within family or disruption of income and socioeconomic ties.

Moreover, not only actual storm events, but also repeated storm threats and recovery efforts lead to stress and anxiety and can negatively impact mental health, increasing the prevalence of depression and anxiety disorders. An analysis of the Adult Psychiatric Morbidity Survey in England, individuals whose homes were damaged from storms have a 50 % higher likelihood of experiencing CMD compared to those whose homes were not damaged (Graham et al. 2019). This analysis also shows that these effects are heterogenous based on age, gender and other socioeconomic features. For example, females have a 105 % higher likelihood of experiencing CMD compared to males. 25–34 years age group has an 8 % lower likelihood of CMD compared to the 16–24 years group. Private renters have a 4 % higher likelihood of CMD, but this is not statistically significant. Inactive individuals have a 31 % higher likelihood of CMD compared to employed individuals. Those in the most deprived areas have a 42 % higher likelihood of CMD compared to those in the least deprived areas. Individuals in poor health have a 2,794 % higher likelihood of CMD compared to those with excellent health.

A study finds that thunderstorms aggravate respiratory issues like asthma and pollen allergy by virtue of osmotic shock from thunder that ruptures pollens releasing allergens, or due to accompanying precipitation that hydrates pollens releasing allergens (D'Amato et al. 2015). It also cites a study in New South Wales, Australia which finds that thunderstorm outflows occurred on 33 % of days when epidemics took place, in contrast to only 3 % of days without epidemics. This suggests that thunderstorm outflows are significantly more frequent on days when epidemics are occurring. Epidemic days refer to specific days on which an outbreak of a disease or illness is happening in a particular population. In this study, these are the days when the incidence of the disease is higher than usual, indicating an epidemic event. The data shows a notable association between the presence of thunderstorm outflows and these epidemic days. This suggests that on those days when asthma epidemics are reported, thunderstorm outflows are significantly more frequent.

Various studies find not only occurrence but also an increase in frequency of thunderstorms due to climate change linked to exacerbation of asthma cases, based on higher observed morbidity levels (D'Amato et al. 2015). Furthermore, some of these studies consider climate change as given and consider higher frequency of thunderstorms as the effect without providing adequate quantitative information. Additionally, these studies find people with existing respiratory ailments to have increased morbidity during thunderstorms. However, there is not enough evidence to establish the causal link due to the complex interactions between thunderstorms, atmosphere and spatiotemporal heterogeneity amongst humans (D'Amato et al. 2015). This is a substantial gap in the literature, where the causal link from climate change to storms to NCDs could be explored.

Another type of storm, the dust storm, has more severe and persistent impact on respiratory diseases like asthma, allergy than thunderstorms due to presence of toxic minerals and particulate matter (Ramirez et al. 2022). The main mechanism of impact from dust storms is like air pollution either from heatwaves (see Section 4.1) or from wildfires (see Section 4.2) or from droughts (see Section 4.4). However, due to the accompanying high-speed winds and volume of toxic minerals and particulate matter, the effects are different. For example, dust storms in USA between 2000 and 2015 have led to 9.2 % increase in respiratory issues related hospital admissions on the day of dust storm and 7.5 % increase on fifth day after dust storm (Rublee et al. 2020). However, the study in previous example could not find significant results for cardiovascular issues although the proportion of hospital admissions for cardiovascular issues is more than double that for respiratory issues. This deviation is not thoroughly explained by the authors. We posit that this could be due to lower level of associated variation between the timing of dust event and cardiovascular issues, which is far lower than that for respiratory issues. As the most prominent and early effect of dust storm leads to respiratory issues. This is a substantial gap that could be addressed with adequate data and research design.

Similar mixed and inadequate evidence is also found in existing systematic literature review on dust storm and its effects on human health (Sadeghimoghaddam et al. 2021). On one hand, it finds some studies conclude that dust storms do not have statistically significant effect on mortality due to respiratory or cardiovascular issues. On the other hand, it also finds studies conclude that dust storms have statistically significant effect on mortality due to respiratory or cardiovascular issues. One reason cited by the authors is due to different consideration of dust type in the dust storm like pm2.5, pm10 etc. Another reason is lack of clarity in explaining the data for type of hospitalisation or mortality cases reported as well as the research design. Furthermore, these studies are quite inconclusive from the aspect of exposure duration, in the sense that some studies find greater effect in short term exposure, some find no effect in short term.

A better understanding is provided by another systematic literature review on effect of storms, super-cyclones, hurricanes and snowstorms on mental health disorders in Asian and South American regions (Rataj, Kunzweiler, and Garthus-Niegel 2016). They find around 40 % increase in psychological morbidity due to these types of storms in the first year of exposure. This trend gradually decreases but persists up to a certain level that varies across countries based on the nature of storm, degree of impact, measurement timing, affected population type etc. Anxiety accounts for the highest incidence followed by depression, especially because the studies that focussed on anxiety included storms that were more devastative in nature. Furthermore, the extent of anxiety and depression observed across the studies are in general lower for less developing countries, due to lower reporting and less mental health awareness.

In conclusion, the findings from the studies are quite conclusive that storms lead to increased health issues due to respiratory, cardiovascular, mental health problems. There are generally higher levels of morbidity, but mortality increases when the duration and intensity of storms increase. Nevertheless, only one systematic review by Sadeghimoghaddam et al. (2021) find that mortality due to cardiovascular issues were highest on first day and that trend decreases day two onwards. These incidents happen only where unpreparedness due to sudden occurrence of event or lack of preparedness due to economic conditions prevail. Additionally, there are studies which do not detail the air pollutants from dust storm as well as specific illnesses pertaining to cardiovascular diseases to ascertain the correct linkage. Even though, the statistical analysis direct towards similar inconclusive findings, as the quality of empirical evidence is still challengeable due to the methods deployed in the studies.

5 Conclusions

Climate change appears to be driving an increase in the frequency and severity of EWEs, which could heighten their impact on NCDs. In recent years, a growing body of research has emerged on this topic, underscoring its increasing relevance and urgency. As climate-related disasters potentially become more frequent and severe, their impact on NCDs is becoming more apparent. The literature suggests that EWEs – including heatwaves, wildfires, flooding, droughts, and storms – may exacerbate existing NCDs and contribute to new health risks. This evidence indicates that climate-induced changes could worsen health outcomes and increase the overall burden of disease.

Heatwaves and elevated temperatures are reported to significantly affect both mortality and morbidity. Most studies suggest that heatwaves exacerbate chronic conditions such as cardiovascular diseases and respiratory disorders. The increased temperatures associated with these events not only raise the risk of heat-related illnesses but could also aggravate pre-existing health problems, particularly for

vulnerable populations. However, the evidence on the impact of heatwaves on mental health remains inconclusive, with studies showing mixed results on whether mental health issues increase following such events.

Wildfires are likely to significantly impact NCDs by worsening respiratory conditions and triggering mental health issues. Air pollution from wildfires, including particulate matter and toxic gases, deteriorates air quality and may aggravate conditions such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and ischaemic heart disease. The oxidative stress and inflammation caused by wildfire emissions could further increase cardiovascular risks. Psychological stress from wildfires is also linked to mental health issues such as anxiety and depression.

Flooding, particularly in communities affected by repeated events, is suggested to have notable long-term psychological effects. Trauma and distress caused by flood damage could lead to persistent mental health disorders such as PTSD, anxiety, and depression. Although some studies indicate that the prevalence of these conditions may decrease over time, mental illness rates often remain higher compared to pre-flood levels. Factors such as household income, flood depth, and the necessity for relocation seem to influence the prevalence of these conditions.

Droughts pose challenges in assessing health impacts due to their gradual onset and complex nature. They result in water deficits and disruptions to agriculture, which may lead to health issues such as heat-related illnesses and mental health problems, including stress and anxiety due to economic distress across the food supply chain. Additionally, the slow development and varying definitions of drought complicate precise measurement of its health effects. The bidirectional linkages of drought with other EWEs, such as heatwaves and wildfires, are not well studied, and existing results may be biased due to the confounding nature of these conditions.

Storms, including cyclones, are likely to impact health through physical stress, displacement, and exposure to pollutants. Increased storm intensity and frequency, potentially driven by climate change, are believed to exacerbate cardiovascular and respiratory conditions. The stress and anxiety associated with storms and recovery efforts could also heighten mental health issues, such as depression and anxiety disorders. However, the health impacts of specific storm types, such as dust storms or super-cyclones, are not typically examined separately in the literature. Moreover, many studies do not explicitly identify specific diseases like asthma, bronchitis, ischaemic heart disease, or heart attacks, making it difficult to draw clear empirical conclusions.

Overall, the evidence suggests that climate-related disasters have significant health impacts on NCDs. Understanding these interactions is crucial for developing effective strategies to address and mitigate the adverse effects of climate change on health. Future research should aim to improve study designs through clearer

identification strategies and the use of robust estimation methodologies. For instance, both qualitative and quantitative elaboration of indicator variables for EWEs and NCDs is essential to ensure that findings have stronger external validity. Additionally, simultaneity between different EWEs (e.g. heatwaves, droughts, storms) and between various NCDs (e.g. cardiovascular and respiratory diseases) can introduce bias in the estimates. These challenges can be addressed with better-measured data and the use of event-study approaches, which would help disentangle the specific impact of individual EWEs on targeted NCDs. This would also facilitate the development of meta-analyses by enabling the use of standardized and comparable indicators, a limitation in the current literature. Finally, future studies should prioritize the use of direct indicators of climate change to assess its impact on NCDs, rather than relying solely on EWEs as proxies for climate change.

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Appendix

Figures A1 and A2

Figure A1: Number of studies per continent in our literature review.

Figure A2: Number of EWEs per category in our literature review.

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